

Synthesis of Lanthanide(III) Complexes with 2-(3-Coumarinylthioacetyl)-benzimidazole

K. B. GUDASI^{a*} and T. R. GOUDAR^b

^aBasaveshwar Science College, Bagalkot-587 101

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad-580 003

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Coumarin and its derivatives have been extensively used for biological and analytical studies¹. In continuation of our earlier work² on metal complexes of coumarin biheterocycles, here we report the synthesis and characterisation of some lanthanide(III) complexes with 2-(3-coumarinylthioacetyl)benzimidazole (CTBz).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) are consistent with the proposed stoichiometry. The molar conductance values reveal their non-electrolytic nature. The μ_{eff} values of the complexes showed slight deviation from the Hund's values as well as Van Vleck values, but are within the predicted range. This indicates little participation of *f* electrons in the bond formation.

Infrared spectrum of the ligand reveal sharp bands at 1 720 and 1 673 cm^{-1} assigned to C=O of lactone carbonyl

and 3-keto group respectively. On complexation, these bands suffered a negative shift, which implies the coordination of lactone carbonyl and 3-keto group to the central lanthanide(III) ion. The band at 1 595 cm^{-1} (C=N) of benzimidazole moiety shifted to lower energy side by 25 cm^{-1} , indicating its participation in coordination. The appearance of broad strong band at 3 500–3 300 cm^{-1} was assigned to ν_{OH} of either water or ethanol. The appearance of an additional band at 1 040 cm^{-1} in case of the spectra of the nitrate complexes suggests the presence of ethanol³. On the other hand, in case of the chloride complexes, the band at 1 040 cm^{-1} is absent and a band has appeared at 840 cm^{-1} . This implies the presence of coordinated water in the chloride complexes. The additional bands at 1 420 and 1 290 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_4 and ν_1 frequencies of coordinated nitrate groups. The extent of separation of ν_4 and ν_1 frequencies (130 cm^{-1}) indicates the presence of nitrate moieties in unidentate fashion⁴. The non-ligand bands of medium intensity observed at 435–430, 360–355 and 330–325 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ln-O}}$, $\nu_{\text{Ln-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ln-Cl}}$ modes respectively.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Ln% : Found/ (Calcd.)	A_{m} $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	Hund value B.M.	Van Vleck value B.M.	Exptl. value B.M.
[La(CTBz)(NO ₃) ₃].3C ₂ H ₅ OH	17.42 (17.35)	35.02	0.00	0.00	Diamag.
[Ce(CTBz)Cl ₃ .2H ₂ O]	22.72 (22.65)	20.34	2.54	2.56	2.50
[Pr(CTBz)Cl ₃ .2H ₂ O]	22.85 (22.75)	19.94	3.78	3.62	3.64
[Nd(CTBz)Cl ₃ .2H ₂ O]	22.85 (23.16)	19.94	3.62	3.68	3.59
[Sm(CTBz)(NO ₃) ₃].3C ₂ H ₅ OH	18.69 (18.56)	17.15	0.84	1.65	2.01
[Gd(CTBz)(NO ₃) ₃].3C ₂ H ₅ OH	19.30 (19.24)	17.6	7.94	7.94	7.85
[Dy(CTBz)(NO ₃) ₃].3C ₂ H ₅ OH	19.98 (19.76)	17.54	10.61	10.61	10.52
[Y(CTBz)(NO ₃) ₃].3C ₂ H ₅ OH	12.00 (11.87)	13.46	0.00	0.00	Diamag.

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Assignment	λ_{\max} of Ln(III) ion cm ⁻¹	λ_{\max} of complex cm ⁻¹	β^1	Other parameters
[Pr(CTBz)Cl ₃ ·2H ₂ O]	$^3P_2 \leftarrow ^3H_4$	22 381.4	22 326.4	0.997 543 4	$\beta^1 = 0.995\ 384\ 3$
	$^3P_1 \leftarrow$	21 222.4	21 132.7	0.995 787 0	$b^{1/2} = 0.033\ 97$
	$^3P_0 \leftarrow$	20 644.1	20 529.7	0.994 458 4	$\eta = 0.002\ 316$
	$^1D_2 \leftarrow$	16 812.4	16 770.1	0.993 748 4	$\delta = 0.463\ 71$
[Nd(CTBz)Cl ₃ ·2H ₂ O]	$^4G_{7/2} \leftarrow ^4I_{9/2}$	18 993.4	18 986.2	0.999 626 0	$\beta^1 = 0.999\ 646\ 3$
	$^4G_{5/2}, ^2G_{7/2} \leftarrow$	17 146.8	17 205.8	1.003 441 0	$b^{1/2} = 0.009\ 4$
	$^4F_{5/2} \leftarrow$	12 459.5	12 437.8	0.998 258 0	$\eta = 0.000\ 177$
	$^4F_{3/2} \leftarrow$	11 446.9	11 415.5	0.997 260 3	$\delta = 0.035\ 378$
[Sm(CTBz)(NO ₃) ₃ ·3C ₂ H ₅ OH]	$^4I_{11/2} \leftarrow ^6H_{5/2}$	20 903.0	20 824.7	0.996 254 1	$\beta^1 = 0.994\ 801\ 2$
	$^4I_{13/2} \leftarrow$	21 552.0	21 459.2	0.992 197 3	$b^{1/2} = 0.036\ 1$
	$^4F_{9/2} \leftarrow$	24 812.0	24 618.4	0.992 177 3	$\eta = 0.002\ 61$
	$^6P_{3/2} \leftarrow$	26 624.0	26 490.0	0.994 966 9	$\delta = 0.522\ 596$

Electronic spectra of the lanthanide(III) complexes are compared with those of the aqueous rare earth salts (Table 2). The data indicate that the energy of *f-f* transitions in the complexes is slightly reduced from the corresponding aquo ions, either because of the slight covalent interaction of the *4f*-orbitals with vacant ligand orbitals leading to some delocalisation with consequent reduction in inter-electronic repulsion⁵ or by increased nuclear shielding of the *4f*-orbitals due to slight covalent ligand-metal electron drift. In the present case, the partial covalent bonding is developed between the lanthanide(III) ion and the ligand. The β values less than unity, δ and $b^{1/2}$ values being small, positive confirm the above findings.

The pmr spectra of CTBz showed two doublets with equal coupling at δ 4.5 and 3.83 assigned to HA and HB type protons of -CH₂- group. The aromatic region exhibits a complex set of multiplets accounting for eight protons at δ 6.68–8.27. The singlet at δ 8.28 is assigned to highly deshielded C₄-H of coumarin. A broad signal at δ 12.62 is due to NH proton. The pmr spectrum of the La^{III} complex exhibited a triplet at δ 1.00 followed by a quartet at δ 2.5 accounting for 3 and 2 protons respectively, suggesting the presence of ethanol molecules in the complexes. On coordination, the two doublets due to HA and HB type protons of -CH₂- group shifted downfield to δ 5.16 and 4.28 respectively. This downfield shift suggests its deshielding because of the coordination of adjacent carbonyl group to the central metal ion. The singlet due to C₄-H of coumarin suffered a downfield shift indicating the involvement of carbonyl group in coordination.

The thermal decomposition pattern of the Gd^{III} complex suggest a three-step decomposition. The complex is stable upto 60°. At 60–110°, the weight-loss of 16.3% on

TG curve corresponds to the loss of three ethanol molecules. The loss of ethanol molecules below 110° suggests them to be lattice-held but not coordinated. This agrees with the observation made on the basis of ir and pmr spectra. The weight of the residue beyond 700° suggests the formation of Gd₂O₃ and agrees with the analytical data for the metal content. The presence of lattice-held ethanol molecules in other nitrate complex is confirmed by the indirect method, which involves heating of the nitrate complexes at 110°. On heating the chloride complexes to 110°, no weight-loss was observed. This indicates the absence of lattice held water or ethanol molecules, which indirectly supports the infrared data for the presence of coordinated water molecules.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of reagent grade. Hydrated lanthanide(III) nitrates were prepared from the respective oxides with nitric acid. The chloride salts (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.; 99.9% pure) were used as such.

The ligand CTBz was prepared by reported method⁶. The complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of the CTBz (0.002 mol) and the lanthanide(III) salt (0.001 mol) in absolute ethanol for 3 h. The pH of the reaction mixture was then raised to 5.5–6.0 by adding ethanolic ammonia and it was further refluxed for 1 h. The resulting complexes were washed and dried under reduced pressure over fused calcium chloride.

The metal content of the complexes was determined by EDTA titration using xylenol orange as the indicator at pH 6. C, H and N were determined using a Perkin-Elmer 240 CHN analyser. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature. Molar conduc-

tance (DMF) was measured using an Elico-CM-82 conductivity bridge. Ir spectra (KBr) and far-ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 5100 and 4367 spectrophotometers, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Hitachi 228-1050 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer. Thermal studies of the complexes were carried out in the temperature range 27–1000°.

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